

DECORATIVE DECORATIONS OF OLD BUILDINGS

Fayzulla Chorshanbayev Ziyatovich

associate professor Chinnigul Meliyeva Otaqulovna - is a senior teacher
Samarkand State of Architecture and Civil Engineering University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

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Abstract: This article explains that the correct selection of local building materials used in the repair of monument patterns and decorations is a necessary process. There are methods of special preparation of building materials used in the repair of architectural monuments of Uzbekistan and the order of their use.

Keywords: Patterns, pottery, tiles, ornaments, girih, islimi, ganch, baked bricks, vinegar, rivets, items, repairs, architectural monuments.

ДЕКОРАТИВНЫЕ УКРАШЕНИЯ СТАРЫХ ЗДАНИЙ

Аннотация: В данной статье объясняется, что правильный выбор местных строительных материалов, используемых при ремонте моделей и украшений памятников, является необходимым процессом. Приведены методы специальной подготовки строительных материалов, применяемых при ремонте памятников архитектуры Узбекистана, и порядок их использования.

Ключевые слова: Узоры, керамика, изразцы, орнаменты, гирих, ислими, ганч, жженный кирпич, укус, заклепки, изделия, ремонт, памятники архитектуры.

INTRODUCTION

The exquisite decoration of the architectural monuments of Uzbekistan arouses great interest not only among foreign tourists, but also among our local people. Decorating buildings with patterns has enriched the spiritual outlook of man since ancient times. Therefore, special attention is paid to the decoration of buildings in architecture. If we look at the unique architectural monuments that have reached us, we can see that the art of decorating them has become richer and more beautiful over time.

MAIN PART

During the construction of the building, we witnessed simultaneous finishing and finishing works. To this day, we know that any architectural monument is destroyed and damaged to a certain extent under the influence of natural factors, and we need to take a scientific approach to them, repair, repair methods, as well as the correct selection of local raw materials. The maintenance of architectural monuments and their decorations is a necessary process that can be repeated in the monument over time.[1]

Picture 1: Tilla Qori madrasa, Samarkand

While analyzing the pattern decorations of our historical monuments, special attention was paid to the correctness of geometric constructions, which represent the general harmony of architectural forms, the art of decorating the exterior and interior of buildings. We can see that during the construction of the building, finishing and finishing works were carried out simultaneously.

Picture 2: Afrosiyob panels

Today, we know that any architectural monument is destroyed to a certain extent and damaged by natural factors, it is necessary to repair them, to take a scientific approach to the methods of repair, and to choose the right local raw materials. Repair of architectural monuments and their patterns is considered a necessary process, and they can be repeated in the monument over time. This usually occurs as a result of damage and destruction of the monument under the influence of natural and man-made factors.[1] It is no secret that a large part of the repair work of architectural monuments is their architectural decoration, that is, the style of the building and the patterns in its interior parts. The simultaneous use of simple and decorative brick and marble patterns formed a whole art. An integral part of the decoration is floral patterns and mixing in harmony with blue and white tiles.

It is known that Uzbekistan is such an attractive historical country that thousands and hundreds of existing architectural and archaeological monuments in its territory require further development of scientific and practical repair and restoration works in this country. A large part of the repair of architectural monuments is their architectural decoration, that is, the style of the building and the patterns in the interior parts. Use of materials in the repair of architectural monuments methods is a problematic topic of scientific, practical and theoretical importance in the field of maintenance and preservation of architectural heritage objects along with the experience and achievements so far, there are also problems and shortcomings specific to this field.[2]

Despite the difficulties of the transitional period in the years of independence, the practice of repairing architectural monuments in the city of Samarkand was under the constant attention of the government of the republic. international and republican practice, but systematically urban planning, architectural and art monuments of the historical area are preserved to this day.

Uzbekistan's historical monuments and towers attract everyone, especially tourists coming to our country, with their magnificence and beautiful patterns. In historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Ko'kan, Shahrisabz, we can see preserved historical monuments, irrevocable views of the art of brickwork, sky-high peaks, minarets, and elegant bouquets.

Over the centuries, all kinds of terrible wars and natural disasters lead to the erosion of the original charm of many monuments, the movement of tiles and the use of structures. Restoring the domes of damaged monuments is an honorable and sacred task, which is mainly carried out by experienced repairmen.[3]

It should be noted that many methods were developed in the use of constructive architectural devices of mosques in medieval architecture. If the methods of transition from corners to circular surfaces were performed using simple wooden beams, conical bagal-tropes were made using bricks, countless methods of transition from murabba (square) to muzam (octagonal) were used.

Since the beginning of the 1920s, in the pottery workshop of the Samarkand scientific repair workshop, which is famous and well-known throughout Uzbekistan, folk craftsmen - Abdugadir Baqiyev, master Usman Umarov from Gijduvan, masters from Samarkand - master Abdugafur, grandfather Mirmuhammad, master Tursunlar have been creating, did .

Then, when the work of the workshop was in full swing, masters Azimmurod Khojayev, Shofi Ishakov, and Nasim Gafurov joined the enterprise. Tashmukum Kurbanov, Kambarov Melik and others are invited. The above tilers are dedicated to their craft in making their products as close as possible to the original in terms of color and quality, so their clay glazed and unglazed brick tiles as well as clay glazed tiles are close to the original in terms of quality. .

"Arhitekturnaya keramika Uzbekistana" (T., 1968) architect and folk masters Abdugafar Haqkulov, Mirzaqul Toirov, Shirin Murodov, Anvar Quliyev, professors M.K. Rahimov, I.E. Pletnev is known for many works in this field. in his monograph A.S. Uralov, A.G. Hakkulov, Sh.M. Abduraimov's monograph "Principles of Repair and Restoration of Architectural Monuments" (Samarkand 2020), A. Hakkulov's "Dedication to the Art of Architectural Repair and Tiling" (Samarkand, 2016) are important in the field. did things. scientific research, M.S. Bulatov, S.P. Zohidov, I.I. Notkin, G.A. Pugachenkova, L.I. Rempellar considered the methodological side of the matter.[4]

For research, it is necessary to clarify that the correct selection of local building materials used in the repair of patterns and decorations of Central Asian architectural monuments is a necessary process. In this, a scientific approach is taken to the correct selection of construction materials used in the repair of architectural monuments of Uzbekistan, gas brick, tile and brick, clay and ganchkhok from angob, special methods of preparation of mixtures, local raw materials for preparation. ganch mixture, analysis, conducting experiments in laboratories and achieving results.

Analysis of methods of using local raw materials in the repair of patterns and decorations of Central Asian architectural monuments. Determining the durability of local building materials in the natural climate of Central Asia.[8]

In order to achieve the set goal, it is planned to solve the following issues:

- To study the traditional methods and practice of updating architecture in Uzbekistan.
- study and analysis of methods of using modern materials in preservation and restoration of architectural monuments.
- use of modern techniques and technologies in the repair of architectural monuments.
- Measures to restore the original local building materials and traditional construction style as much as possible in the construction of the monument-

Identifying deficiencies and mistakes made in the repair of architectural monument decorations, conducting laboratory work, developing recommendations for their elimination, using local raw materials in the preservation, repair and restoration of architectural monument decorations and patterns; as well as the monument itself, the durability of local building materials. clarifying and revealing legal norms in their use constitutes a scientific innovation.

Repairing the decoration of architectural monuments, ensuring their attractiveness, preserving monuments as a cultural heritage for future generations, and using them for modern purposes is also important.[1]

CONCLUSION

Attention is paid to the tile decorations, their types, and the process of their preparation, which are most often used in architectural monuments and are used in their repair. After all, as we mentioned above, we all know that most of the architectural repair work consists of architectural decorations. Based on this, we tried to explain the technology of raw materials and materials, the preparation and restoration of decorations in the repair of tiles in monuments using a scientific approach and analysis.

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